

LEGAL RESPONSIBILITY FOR VIOLATION OF THE RIGHTS OF CONSUMERS AT IMPLEMENTATION OF MARKET RESEARCHES

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Abstract:

This article explores the legal framework governing the responsibilities and liabilities associated with the violation of consumer rights during the execution of market research activities. It delves into the interplay between economic and legal mechanisms to achieve effective market research outcomes, emphasizing the necessity for marketing professionals to possess a comprehensive understanding of both marketing procedures and their alignment with legal norms and societal expectations.

Keywords: marketing research, competition, consumer rights.

Experience has demonstrated that the most effective results from marketing research can be achieved through a comprehensive approach that combines economic and legal strategies to influence the market. Training marketers and applying practical skills have made it clear that marketing experts need to possess not only professional marketing techniques but also the ability to integrate their knowledge with legal regulations and societal norms.¹

It is a well-known fact that marketers conduct specific market research, based on which they provide recommendations to interested parties for their future actions. This can lead to various challenges, such as determining the best approach to construct an advertising campaign, conducting consumer surveys in a lawful manner without infringing on the dignity of respondents, and choosing the most suitable distribution channel (either independent product distribution or utilizing intermediaries like proxies, commission agents, or agents). Marketers must have a deep understanding of the legal avenues that can enhance the effectiveness of using marketing research.²

In this context, it is crucial to highlight that a substantial portion of market dynamics examined by marketers involves consumers. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On protection of consumer rights” dated April 26, 1996, No. 221 defines a consumer as a citizen (physical person) who buys goods, orders to

¹ Frey, C. J., & Kinnear, T. C. (1979). Legal Constraints and Marketing Research: Review and Call to Action. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 16(3), 295–302. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3150703>

² Karaseva M.V. (2013). Responsibility for violation of consumer rights during marketing research. *Bulletin of the Moscow University of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Russia*, (12), 169-173.

perform works or provide services for personal consumption or other purpose, not connected with profit who has this intention.³

Consumer relationships represent a fundamental aspect of economic transactions involving goods, works, and services. Consequently, knowledge of consumer rights and the legal repercussions for violating these rights, as stipulated by the law, is vital for effectively conducting marketing research. Within the scope of this work, it is necessary to refer to the core principles of Uzbek legislation concerning accountability for breaches of consumer rights.

For the violation of consumer rights, the manufacturer (executor, seller, authorized organization, or authorized individual entrepreneur, importer) is subject to civil legal liability as provided by law or contract.

When it comes to the definition of marketing research will be given following notions:

“Marketing research is the method used by marketers to collect an array of data that is useful to a company in soliciting business. Marketers have shifted their strategy to focus more on relationship marketing. This marketing technique provides companies with more detailed descriptions of personal behavior by uncovering customer specific wants and needs. In having this information, marketers are able to decide the best way in which to satisfy these wants and needs.⁴This type of specified and personalized information provides far more value as opposed to characteristics of an overall large sample, as it leads to long-term buyer-seller relationships.⁵

However, there are some aspects which must be taken into account that one of them may violate consumers’ rights for privacy ⁶

In general, market research plays a pivotal role in shaping business strategies, guiding product development, and ensuring consumer satisfaction. However, the process of gathering data and conducting research must always be carried out with the utmost respect for consumer rights and legal obligations. ⁷This article explores the legal responsibilities and consequences associated with the violation of consumer rights during the implementation of market research.

³ <https://lex.uz/docs/14643#17188>

⁴ Frank Franzak et al., Online Relationships and the Consumer’s Right to Privacy, 18 THE J. OF CONSUMER MKTG. 631, 639 (2021)

⁵ Johnson, Hadley (2022) "Marketing Research and Children’s Consumer Privacy Rights: A Battle in the Digital Age," Child and Family Law Journal: Vol. 10: Iss. 1, Article 5.

⁶ Pridmore, Jason, and David Lyon, '5. Marketing as Surveillance: Assembling Consumers as Brands', in Detlev Zwick, and Julien Cayla (eds), Inside Marketing: Practices, Ideologies, Devices (Oxford, 2011; online edn, Oxford Academic, 1 May 2011),

⁷ Summary Principles of Marketing (Kotler)

The Importance of Consumer Rights. Consumer rights are fundamental in any market economy. They encompass a range of entitlements, including the right to accurate information, the right to privacy, the right to fair treatment, and the right to be protected against fraud or misinformation.⁸ Market research must respect and uphold these rights at every stage of the process.

Legal Framework for Consumer Protection. In most countries, consumer protection laws are in place to safeguard the interests and rights of individuals in their role as consumers. These laws impose obligations on businesses, including those conducting market research, to ensure that consumer rights are not infringed upon.

Common Violations During Market Research are the following:

- **Privacy Violations:** Consumer information must be handled with the utmost care and confidentiality. Unauthorized sharing or misuse of personal data, such as contact information, preferences, or habits, is a breach of privacy and can result in severe legal consequences.
- **Misleading Practices:** Market research findings should be based on truthful and accurate information. Misleading statements, false advertising, or biased research can lead to allegations of deception and legal action.
- **Coercion and Manipulation:** Participants in market research should engage willingly, free from undue pressure. Coercion, manipulation, or the use of deceptive tactics to influence responses can violate consumer rights and lead to legal trouble.
- **Failure to Obtain Informed Consent:** Informed consent is essential before collecting data from consumers. Without proper consent, the research may be considered unethical and unlawful.

When businesses or individuals conducting market research fail to uphold consumer rights, they may face various legal consequences:

1. **Civil Liability:** Violations can lead to lawsuits by affected consumers seeking compensation for damages, including financial losses and emotional distress.

Particularly according to provisions of Law on Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On protection of consumer rights” dated April 26, 1996, No. 221 Articles of 22 ,27⁹ and the legal norms of Civil Code of Uzbekistan¹⁰ regulates the liability and the right for compensation in the state of violation

⁸ <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/46/consumer-policy-principles-and-instruments>

⁹ <https://lex.uz/docs/14643#17188>

¹⁰ <https://lex.uz/docs/5535095>

2. **Administrative Penalties:** Regulatory authorities may impose fines or other administrative penalties for violations of consumer protection laws. For instance, in conformity with the Regulation “On the procedure for initiating and considering cases of violations of competition law, natural monopolies, consumer rights protection, and advertising”¹¹ the order of how administrative cases are filed ¹²is well-detailed written. Liability for offence is considered in the Code of The Republic of Uzbekistan on Administrative Responsibility.¹³
3. **Reputation Damage:** Legal violations can harm a business's reputation, leading to lost trust and decreased consumer confidence.
4. **Criminal Charges:** In some extreme cases, intentional violations of consumer rights may lead to criminal charges, particularly if fraud or deception is involved.

In conclusion, market research is an invaluable tool for understanding and serving consumers, but it must be conducted with the highest ethical standards and respect for consumer rights. Violations can result in severe legal consequences, including civil liability, fines, and reputation damage. To avoid these pitfalls, businesses and researchers must remain vigilant in upholding consumer rights throughout the research process. Ultimately, legal responsibility for the violation of consumer rights in the implementation of market research is a critical aspect of ensuring the ethical and lawful conduct of this essential business practice.

It appears that marketers' awareness of the fundamental provisions of Uzbek consumer protection legislation described above will not only contribute to the observance of consumer rights but also enhance the quality and effectiveness of marketing research.

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¹¹ www.lex.uz/docs/-111189

¹² <https://lex.uz/docs/878601>

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